

ISic1362

Funerary inscription for Leontia and Kalliope

Language

Type

Material

Object

Editor

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Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di
Catania, inventory 541

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 19.5 cm

Width 29.5 cm

Depth 2 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Lines 1-9: 8-25 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

1. ἐν
2. θάδε
3. κίτε Λε
4. οντία ἐτῶ (ν)
5. γ'.
6. ἐνθάδε κί
7. τε Καλλι
8. όπη ἐτῶ (ν)
9. menorah ιη'. menorah etrog?

Apparatus

Translation (en)

Here lies Leontia, aged 3. Here lies Kalliope, aged 18.

Translation (it)

Qui giace Leontia di anni 3. Qui giace Calliope di anni 18.

Commentary

The formula *enthade kite* (*keitai*) is normally found in Christian inscriptions in Sicily, but the presence of menorahs and what is perhaps an *etrog* (a type of citron, used in the festival of Sukkot) show this to be a Jewish text. Leontia is an uncommon name, also attested in Syracuse and perhaps intended as a Greek translation for the Jewish name Judith; Kalliope is more common among Jews and non-Jews, and attested in Catania and Syracuse. The two girls were presumably related, perhaps sisters?

Digital identifiers:

TM 491452

EDCS 38000201

PHI 140866

PHI 316312

Bibliography

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